

**Catalogue of Afghanistan Longhorn beetles
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) with two descriptions of new
Phytoecia (*Parobereina* Danilevsky, 2018) from Central Asia**

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Abstract: The Catalogue includes all 78 Cerambycidae species of Afghanistan fauna known up to 2019 with the references to the original descriptions; 22 species were not mentioned for Afghanistan in Palaearctic Cerambycidae Catalogue by Löbl & Smetana (2010). Bibliography of each species usually includes the geographical information from corresponding publications. Many new taxonomy positions published after 2010 are used here without special remarks. *Agapanthia* (*Epoptes*) *dahli ustynovi* Danilevsky, 2013 **stat. nov.** is downgraded from the species level. Two species are described as new *Phytoecia* (*Parobereina*) *pashtunica* **sp. n.** from Afghanistan and *Phytoecia* (*Parobereina*) *heinzi* **sp.n.** from Pakistan.

The present work is an attempt to summarize all data published up to now on Cerambycidae of Afghanistan fauna.

Family **CERAMBYCIDAE** Latreille, 1802

subfamily **Prioninae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Macrotomini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Anomophysis* Quentin & Villiers, 1981: 374 type species

Prionus spinosus Fabricius, 1787

inscripta C.O. Waterhouse, 1884: 380 (*Macrotoma*)

Heyrovský, 1936: 211 - Wama; Tippmann, 1958: 41 - Kabul, Ost-Afghanistan, 1740; Sarobi, am Kabulfluss, 900 m; Mangul, Bashgultal, Nuristan, Ost-Afghanistan, 1250 m; Fuchs, 1961: 259 - Sarobi 1100 m, O.-Afghanistan; Fuchs, 1967: 432 - Afghanistan, 25 km N von Barikot, 1800 m, Nuristan; Nimla, 40 km SW von Dschelalabad; Heyrovský, 1967: 156 - Zentral-Afghanistan, Prov. Kabul: Kabul; Kabul-Zahir; Ost-Afghanistan, Prov. Nengrahar:

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“Nuristan”, ohne näheren Fundort; Kamu; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 90 - Afghanistan.

plagiata C.O. Waterhouse, 1884: 381 (*Macrotoma*)

vidua Lameere, 1903: 167 (*Macrotoma*)

Quentin & Villiers, 1981: 361, 376, 383 - Afghanistan: Kaboul; Sairobi; Darah-i-Nour, Nangahar; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 90 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 267 - Afghanistan: Kaboul; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 64 - Afghanistan.

tribe Prionini Latreille, 1802

genus *Dorysthenes* Vigers, 1826: 514 type species *Prionus rostratus* Fabricius, 1793

subgenus *Lophosternus* Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 209 type species *Lophosternus buquetii* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

Cyrtosternus Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 210 type species *Lophosternus hopei* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

huegelii L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 550 (*Cyrtognathus*)

falco J. Thomson, 1877: 262 (*Cyrtognathus*)

palpalis Gahan, 1906: 12 (*Lophosternus*)

Note: *D. huegelii* was recorded for Afghanistan (Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 91; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 65), and the occurrence of the species in the country is rather probable, but no exact locality information was published up to now, and the corresponding specimens are not known.

genus *Mesoprionus* Jakovlev, 1887: 323 type species *Prionus asiaticus* Faldermann, 1837

angustatus Jakovlev, 1887: 327 (*Prionus*)

angheri Brancsik, 1899: 102 (*Prionus*)

bucharicus Semenov, 1900: 328 (*Prionus*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 92 - Afghanistan; Danilevsky, 2014b: 45 - North Afghanistan.

genus *Miniprionus* Danilevsky, 2000: 189 type species *Prionus pavlovskii* Semenov, 1935

pavlovskii Semenov, 1935: 239 (*Prionus*)

Danilevsky, 2000: 190 - North Afghanistan.

genus *Pogonarthron* Semenov, 1900: 257 type species *Polyarthron bedeli* Semenov, 1900

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subgenus *Multicladum* Danilevsky in Danilevsky & Komiya, 2014:
268 type species *Prionus semenovianus* Plavilstshikov, 1936
semenovianum Plavilstshikov, 1936: 92 (*Prionus*)
Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 93 - Afghanistan; Danilevsky, 2014b: 62 -
North Afghanistan.

genus *Prionus* Geoffroy, 1762: 198 type species *Cerambyx*
coriarius Linnaeus, 1758

corpulentus Bates, 1878: 720

Fuchs, 1955: 272, 273 - Pashki, Nuristan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 93
- Afghanistan.

elliotti Gahan, 1906: 16

Gahan, 1906: 16 - Baluchistan, near Quetta; Koh-i-Baba: Marrak;
Fuchs, 1955: 271 - Marrak, Koh-i-Baba, Afghanistan; Shirparak,
Koh-i-Baba, Afghanistan; Tippmann, 1958: 41 - Senna, Kokschatal,
Badakschan, NO-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 94 -
Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 273 - Afghanistan, Koh-i-Baba,
Marrak.

vartianorum Fuchs, 1967: 431

Fuchs, 1967: 431 - Afghanistan: Paghman, 30 km NW von Kabul,
2500 m; Khurd-Kabul [34°23'N, 69°23'E], SO von Kabul, 1900 m;
Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 94 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 66 -
Afghanistan.

genus *Pseudoprionus* Pic, 1898: 33 type species *Polyarthron*
bienerti Heyden, 1885

altimontanus Kabakow & Dolin, 1996: 45 (*Prionus*)

Kabakow & Dolin, 1996: 45 - Afghanistan: Prov. Uruzdan, N von
Schachrestan; SW Panjav / Qonay Pass; Zabolj Prov., W von
Argandab; Danilevsky, 2009: 293 - Central Afghanistan; Löbl &
Smetana, 2010: 94 - Afghanistan.

subfamily **Lepturinae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Lepturini Latreille, 1802

genus *Anastrangalia* Casey, 1924: 280 type species *Leptura*
sanguinea LeConte, 1859

rubriola Bates, 1878: 720 (*Leptura*)

kashmirica Plavilstshikov, 1927: 105

Heyrovský, 1936: 211 - Parun-Tal; Schigi; Löbl & Smetana, 2010:
97 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 66 - Afghanistan.

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genus *Pedostrangalia* Sokolov, 1897: 461 type species
Pedostrangalia kassjanowi Sokolov, 1897 (= *Leptura imberbis*
Ménétriés, 1832)

subgenus *Pedostrangalia* Sokolov, 1897: 461 type species
Pedostrangalia kassjanowi Sokolov, 1897 (= *Leptura imberbis*
Ménétriés, 1832)

afghanistana Satô & N. Ohbayashi, 1976: 485

Satô & N. Ohbayashi, 1976: 485 - Kabul, Aliabad; Löbl & Smetana,
2010: 110 - Afghanistan.

imberbis Ménétriés, 1832: 231 (*Leptura*)

angulicollis Heyden, 1879: 323 [=1879: 67] (*Strangalia*)

kassjanowi Sokolov, 1897: 461

Özdikmen, 2004: 24, 28 - Afghanistan.

subgenus *Neosphenalia* Löbl, 2010: 60 type species *Leptura*
verticalis Germar, 1822

Sphenalia K. Daniel, 1904: 355 [HN] type species *Leptura verticalis* Germar,
1822

? *kurda* Sama, 1996: 104

Nota. The record of *P.emmipoda* (Mulsant, 1863) for
Afghanistan by Özdikmen (2004: 25, 28) had to be connected
with *P. kurda* Sama, 1996, but later Özdikmen (2014: 403) did
not include Afghanistan in the general area of *P.emmipoda*.

genus *Rutpela* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1957: 242 type species
Leptura maculata Poda von Neuhaus, 1761

inermis K. Daniel & J. Daniel, 1898: 74 (*Strangalia*)

elboursensis Pic, 1905: 390 (*Strangalia*)

Heyrovský, 1971: 82 - Hérat, province d'Hérat, Afghanistan
septentrional.

tribe Rhagiini Kirby, 1837

genus *Cortodera* Mulsant, 1863: 572 type species *Grammoptera*
spinosula Mulsant, 1839: 290 (= *Leptura humeralis* Schaller, 1783)

bamiyana Danilevsky, 2014a: 256

Danilevsky, 2014a: 256 - Afghanistan, Bamiyan, Panjab Distr.,
Varas; Özdikmen, 2016: 14 - Afghanistan.

Note. The records of *Cortodera transcaspica persica*
Plavilstshikov, 1936 and *C. pseudomoplus* Reitter, 1889 for

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Afghanistan by Özdikmen (2003) were most probably based on wrong determination of local species.

subfamily **Apatophyseinae** Lacordaire, 1869

tribe Apatophyseini Lacordaire, 1869

genus *Apatophysis* Chevrolat, 1860a: 95 type species *Apatophysis toxotoides* Chevrolat, 1860 (= *Polyarthron barbarum* P. H. Lucas, 1858)

subgenus *Angustephysis* Pic, 1956: 2 type species *Apatophysis richteri* Pic, 1956

margiana Semenov & Shchegoleva-Barovskaya, 1936: 77

plavilstshikovi Miroshnikov, 1992: 392

Danilevsky, 2008: 37, 41 - North Afghanistan

modica Gahan, 1906: 71

Danilevsky, 2006: 9 - south Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 142 - Afghanistan.

subgenus *Apatophysis* Chevrolat, 1860a: 95 type species *Apatophysis toxotoides* Chevrolat, 1860 (= *Polyarthron barbarum* P. H. Lucas, 1858)

afghanica Miroshnikov, 2014: 14

Miroshnikov, 2014: 14 - Afghanistan, Paktya, Spera.

caspica Semenov, 1901: 31

Danilevsky, 2006: 2 - Afghanistan; 2008: 22, 41 - Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 142 - Afghanistan.

genus *Protapatophysis* Semenov & Stschegoleva-Barovskaia, 1936: 26 type species *Apatophysis kashmiriana* Semenov, 1901

kabakovi Danilevsky, 2011: 102

Heyrovský, 1936: 211 (as *A. kashmirina* Semenov, 1901) - Wama; Tippmann, 1958: 47 (as *A. kashmirina* Semenov, 1901) - Kamdesch, 2000 m, Bashgultal, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan; Fuchs, 1967: 433 - Afghanistan, Khurd-Kabul, SO von Kabul, 1900 m (as *A. kashmirina* Semenov, 1901) and Afghanistan, Paghman, 30 km NW von Kabul, 2500 m (as *A. montana* Gahan, 1906); Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 142 - Afghanistan (as *A. vartianae* Heyrovský, 1971); Danilevsky, 2011: 101, 104 - Afghanistan, prov. Kunar, SW Pech-Dara; North-east Afghanistan, West of Konar province (Chapa Dara district).

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subfamily **Cerambycinae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Achrysonini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Nortia* J. Thomson, 1864: 252 type species *Nortia cavicollis*
J. Thomson, 1864

afghanica Heyrovský, 1967: 158

Heyrovský, 1967: 157, 158 - Ost-Afghanistan, Prov. Nengrahar:
Kamu, 1450 m; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 143 - Afghanistan.

tribe Callichromatini Swainson & Shuckard, 1840

genus *Osphranteria* L. Redtenbacher, 1850: 50 type species
Osphranteria suaveolens L. Redtenbacher, 1850

Quettania Schwarzer, 1931: 62 type species *Quettania coeruleipennis*
Schwarzer, 1931.

coerulescens L. Redtenbacher, 1850: 50

inaurata Holzschuh, 1981: 98

coeruleipennis Schwarzer, 1931a: 63 (*Quettania*)

mirabilis Podany, 1980: 231 (*Polyzonus*)

Note. The species must occur in Afghanistan as it is
distributed in Pakistan and in Iran.

lata Pic, 1956: 3

richteri Heyrovský, 1959: 4

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 149 - Afghanistan; Bentanachs, 2012a: 88,
89, 96 - Afghanistan; 2012b: 71 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019:
72 - Afghanistan.

suaveolens L. Redtenbacher, 1850: 50

Heyrovský, 1967: 157 - Ost-Afghanistan, Prov. Nengrahar: Kamu;
Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 149 - Afghanistan; Bentanachs, 2012a: 88,
90, 96 - Afghanistan; 2012b: 71 - Afghanistan.

tribe Callidiini Kirby, 1837

genus *Turanium* Baeckmann, 1922: 32 type species
Callidiumscabrum Kraatz, 1882

subgenus *Turanium* Baeckmann, 1922: 32 type species
Callidiumscabrum Kraatz, 1882

scabrum Kraatz, 1882a: 115 (*Callidium*)

simplarium Heyden, 1885: 296 (*Callidium*)

Danilevsky, 2001: 580 - North Afghanistan (no specimens from the
country known).

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tribe Cerambycini Latreille, 1802

genus *Trirachys* Hope, 1843: 63 type species *Trirachys orientalis*
Hope, 1843

Trirhachis Agassiz, 1846: 378 [unjustified emendation]

Trirrhachys Gemminger, 1872: 2801 [unjustified emendation]

indicola Bates, 1891: 21 (*Neocerambyx*)

Heyrovský, 1936: 211 - Wama [35°11'N 70°48'E]; Löbl & Smetana,
2010: 158 - Afghanistan.

sarta Solsky, 1871: 150 (*Pachydissus*)

Fuchs, 1955: 273 - Kabul; 1967: 433 - Afghanistan, Paghman, 30 km
NW von Kabul, 2500 m; Tippmann, 1958: 45- Kabul, 1740 m, O-
Afghanistan; Bashgultal, 1300 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan;
Pagmangebirge, 2300 m, Ost-Afghanistan; Kandahar, 950 m, Süd-
Afghanistan; Darufulun, bei Kabul, O-Afghanistan, 1800 m; Fuchs,
1961: 259 - Kabul; Polichomri N.-Afghanistan, 700 m; Heyrovský,
1967: 156 - Zentral-Afghanistan, Prov. Kabul: Kabul; Hua, 2002:
191 - Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 158- Afghanistan;
Kumawat et al., 2015: 7895 - Afghanistan; Vitali, Gouverneur &
Chemin, 2017: 46, 48 - Afghanistan, Kaboul, Darulaman; Kariyanna
et al., 2017: 36 - Afganistan: Kabul; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 68 -
Afghanistan.

genus *Derolus* Gahan, 1891: 26 type species *Hammaticherus*

mauritanicus Buquet, 1840

Capnocerambyx Reitter, 1894: 356 type species *Hammaticherus mauritanicus*
Buquet, 1840

iranensis Pic, 1956: 3

iranensis iranensis Pic, 1956: 3

iranensis Lepesme & Breuning, 1958: 179 [HN]

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 159 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 70 -
Afghanistan.

genus *Diorthus* Gahan, 1891: 27 type species *Hammaticherus*

simplex A. White, 1853 (= *Cerambyx cinereus* Fabricius, 1793)

subgenus *Diorthus* Gahan, 1891: 27 type species *Hammaticherus*

simplex A. White, 1853 (= *Cerambyx cinereus* Fabricius, 1793)

cinereus Fabricius, 1793: 265 (*Cerambyx*) [NP]

holosericeus Olivier, 1795: 14 (*Cerambyx*)

inclemens J. Thomson, 1865: 576 (*Pachydissus*)

simplex A. White, 1853: 130 (*Hammaticherus*)

sordidus Pascoe, 1888: 491 (*Neocerambyx*)

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vernicosus Pascoe, 1859: 19 (*Cerambyx*)

Fuchs, 1961: 259 - Kabul; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 160 - Afghanistan;

Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 69 - Afghanistan.

genus *Hoplocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1864: 229 type species

Hammaticherus spinicornis Newman, 1842

spinicornis Newman, 1842a: 245 (*Hammaticherus*)

minor Pic, 1923: 8 (*Hoplocerambyx*)

morosus Pascoe, 1857: 92 (*Cerambyx*)

relictus Pascoe, 1866: 528

Gahan, 1906: 131 - South Afghanistan; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981:

188 - Afghanistan; Hüdepohl, 1990: 65 - Afghanistan; Niisato, 1990:

112 - Afghanistan; Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 51 - South

Afghanistan; Hua, 2002: 211 - Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010:

160 - Afghanistan; Nga, Long & Thinh, 2014: 434 - Afghanistan;

Kumawat et al., 2015: 7895 - Afghanistan; Majumder et al., 2015:

8244 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 31 - South Afghanistan)

genus *Neoplocaederus* Sama, 1991: 123 [RN] type species

Plocaederus cyanipennis J. Thomson, 1861

scapularis Fischer von Waldheim, 1821: 15 (*Cerambyx*)

tataricus Gebler, 1841: 375 (*Hammaticherus*)

Waterhouse, 1889: 130 - Afghanistan, Hari-rud valley; Fuchs, 1961:

259 - Polichomri N.-Afghanistan, 700 m; Fuchs, 1967: 433 -

Afghanistan, Khurd-Kabul, SO von Kabul, 1900 m; Villiers, 1967:

354 - Nord de l'Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 162 -

Afghanistan; Kotán & Sama, 2011: 59 - Afghanistan.

genus *Xenopachys* Sama, 1999: 46 type species *Dissopachys*

matthiesseni Reitter, 1907

matthiesseni Reitter, 1907: 218 (*Dissopachys*)

Fuchs, 1967: 433 - Afghanistan, 25 km N von Barikot, 1300 m,

Nuristan; Heyrovský, 1967: 157 - Ost-Afghanistan, Prov. Nengrahar:

Kamu.

schurmanni Sama, 1999: 46

Sama, 1999: 46 - Afghanistan: Ghov., Jam; Löbl & Smetana, 2010:

162 - Afghanistan.

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tribe Clytini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Chlorophorus* Chevrolat, 1863: 290 type species *Callidium annulare* Fabricius, 1787

subgenus *Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 536 type species *Cerambyx figuratus* Scopoli, 1763

quatuordecimmaculatus Chevrolat, 1863: 295 (*Anthoboscus*)

guerryi Pic, 1902: 30 (*Clytanthus*)

Tippmann, 1958: 54 - Firgamu, Kokschatal, Badakschan, 2300 m, NO-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 168 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 46 - Afghanistan.

subgenus *Immaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 536 type species *Chlorophorus kanoi* Hayashi, 1963

faldermanni Faldermann, 1837: 269 (*Clytus*)

caucasicus Pic, 1897: 262 (*Clytanthus*)

mesmini Pic, 1908: 3 (*Clytanthus*)

punctomaculatus Pic, 1893: 26 (*Clytus*)

quinquemaculatus Gebler, 1845: 104 (*Clytus*)

Tippmann, 1958: 51 - Kamdesch, Bashgultal, 2000 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan; Kutiau, 1500 m, Ost-Nuristan, Afghanistan; Villiers, 1967: 361 - Nord Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 166-Afghanistan)

varius O. F. Müller, 1766: 188

varius varius O. F. Müller, 1766: 188

Tippmann, 1958: 51 - Schiva, Hochsteppe 2800 m, Badakschan, NO-Afghanistan.

genus *Perissus* Chevrolat, 1863: 262 type species *Perissus x-littera* Chevrolat, 1863

delerei Tippmann, 1958: 49

Tippmann, 1958: 49 - Bashgultal, 1100 m, Nuristan, O. Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 175 - Afghanistan.

genus *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860b: 456 type species *Clytus sartorii* Chevrolat, 1860

subgenus *Turanoclytus* Sama, 1994: 325 type species *Clytus namanganensis* Heyden, 1885

namanganensis Heyden, 1885: 297 (*Clytus*)

bucharensis Semenov, 1893: 501 (*Clytus*)

subcrucifer Pic, 1903: 4

Gressitt, 1951: 249 - Afghanistan; Hua, 2002: 236 - Afghanistan.

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subgenus *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860b: 456 type species *Clytus sartorii* Chevrolat, 1860

badachschanicus Tippmann, 1958: 48

Tippmann, 1958: 48 - Firgamu, Kokschatal, 2300 m, Badakschan, NO-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 181- Afghanistan.

smei Laporte & Gory, 1841: 37 (*Clytus*)

Ahmad, 1946: 35, 44 - Kabul; Heyrovský, 1971: 82 - Afghanistan oriental, 30 km au Nord de Kaboul; Majumder et al., 2015: 8245 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 79 - Afghanistan (Kabul); Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 72 - Afghanistan.

stebbingi Gahan, 1906: 244

Tippmann, 1958: 48 - Kabul, 1740 m, Ost-Afghanistan; Fuchs, 1961: 259 - Kabul; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 183 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 63 - Afganistan.

tribe Hesperophanini Mulsant, 1839

subtribe Daramina Sama, 2008

genus *Zodes* Pascoe, 1867: 319 type species *Stromatium maculatum* A. White, 1855

Cornutaemospila Pic, 1927: 30 type species *Cornutaemospila piceosignata* Pic, 1927

compressus Fabricius, 1787: 153 (*Callidium*)

Fuchs, 1967: 433 - Afghanistan, 25 km N von Barikot, 1300 m, Nuristan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 187 - Afghanistan.

tribe Oemini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Noserius* Pascoe, 1857: 95 type species *Noserius tibialis* Pascoe, 1857

indicus Gahan, 1906: 104 (*Hypoeshrus*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 194- Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 79 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 67 - Afghanistan.

tribe Purpuricenini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Afghanicenus* Heyrovský, 1941: 36 type species *Purpuricenus nuristanicus* Heyrovský, 1936

dreesi Tippmann, 1958: 57

Tippmann, 1958: 57- Kamu, Bashgultal, 1500 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan; Bashgultal, 1200 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan; Kutiau, 1450 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 196 - Afghanistan.

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nuristanicus Heyrovský, 1936: 212 (*Purpuricen*)

Heyrovský, 1936: 211, 212 - Gulan-Tal; Brubrutz im Kti-Tal; Kti-Tal; Heyrovský, 1941: 37, 39 - Afghanistan or., Nuristan; Tippmann, 1958: 56 - Pagman-Gebirge, 2300 m, O-Afghanistan; Bashgultal, 1200 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 196 - Afghanistan.

genus *Purpuricen* Dejean, 1821: 105 type species *Cerambyx kaehler* Linnaeus, 1758

Acanthoptera Latreille, 1829: 114 type species *Cerambyx budensis* Götze, 1783

Cyclodera A. White, 1846: 510 type species *Cyclodera quadrinotata* A. White, 1846

Hamadrias Gistel, 1848: 130 [unnecessary substitute name]

Philagathes J. Thomson, 1864: 196 type species *Philagathes laetus* J. Thomson, 1864

Porphyrocenus Reitter, 1913: 34 type species *Purpuricen spectabilis* Motschulsky, 1858

Sternoplistes Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 224 type species *Purpuricen temminckii* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

indus Semenov, 1908: 261 [RN]

haussknechti Gahan, 1906: 186

Ahmad, 1946: 35, 44 - Afghanistan, Darra-i-Khail; Tippmann, 1958: 55 - Bashgultal, Nuristan, 1200 m, O-Afghanistan; Heyrovský, 1967: 157-Ost-Afghanistan, Prov. Nengrahar: Kamu, 1450 m; Miroshnikov & Lobanov, 1990: 17 - Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 198 - Afghanistan; Ambrus & Tichý, 2017: 95 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 78 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 72 - Afghanistan.

kabakovi Miroshnikov & Lobanov, 1990: 15

Miroshnikov & Lobanov, 1990: 15 - Afghanistan: Nuristan, Pech River, SW Chapadar, 2000-2400 m; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 198 - Afghanistan; Danilevsky, 2012b: 149 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 78 - Afghanistan: Nuristan, SW Chanadar; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 71 - Afghanistan.

montanus A. White, 1853: 138

Ambrus & Tichý, 2017: 96 - Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 199 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 71 - Afghanistan.

tribe Tillomorphi Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Cleroclytus* Kraatz, 1884: 226 type species *Cleroclytus semirufus* Kraatz, 1884

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- subgenus** *Cleroclytus* Kraatz, 1884: 226 type species *Cleroclytus semirufus* Kraatz, 1884
semirufus Kraatz, 1884: 225
semirufus collaris Jakovlev, 1885: 290
 manifestus Jakovlev, 1900: 664
 strigicollis Jakovlev, 1900: 663
 Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 206 - Afghanistan.
semirufus semirufus Kraatz, 1884: 225
 Heyden, 1894: 83 - Afghanistan, Kischlak-Tusch.

subfamily Lamiinae Latreille, 1825

tribe Agapanthiini Mulsant, 1839

- genus** *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835: 35 type species
 Cerambyx cardui Linnaeus, 1767
subgenus *Epoptes* Gistel, 1857a:93 [1857b: 605] type species *Lamia asphodeli* Latreille, 1804
 Agapanthiella Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 126 type species *Cerambyx villosa viridescens* DeGeer, 1775
dahli C. F. W. Richter, 1821: pl. 12
dahli ustynovi Danilevsky, 2013: 35, **stat. nov.**
 Note. Afghanistan, Badakhshān province. The taxon was described from Tadzhikistan, but just from the borderline with Afghanistan.
detrita Kraatz, 1882b: 336
 Heyden, 1894: 83 - Afghanistan, Kischlak-Tusch; Tippmann, 1958: 60.
nigriventris C. O. Waterhouse, 1889: 130
 Waterhouse, 1889: 130 -Afghanistan, Hari-rud valley; Winkler, 1929: 1212 - Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 216 - Afghanistan.
paki Rapuzzi, 2012: 958
 Rapuzzi, 2012: 958 - Afghanistan: Ghor prov., 16 km E Chagcharan, Bandi-Ali vill. env.
subgenus *Stichodera* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 126 type species
 Saperda irrorata Fabricius, 1787
soror Kraatz, 1882b: 336
 Tippmann, 1958: 61 - Schiva, Hochsteppe, 2800 m, Badakschan, NO-Afghanistan.

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tribe Apodasyini Lacordaire, 1872

genus *Cylindilla* Bates, 1884: 250 type species *Cylindilla griseescens* Bates, 1884

Anaesthetomorphus Pic, 1929a: 6 [RN] type species *Pseudanesthetis apicalis* Pic, 1929 (= *Cylindilla griseescens* Bates, 1884)

Ascoldatimura Breuning, 1960: 27 [RN] type species *Atimura ascoldensis* Heyden, 1884 (= *Cylindilla griseescens* Bates, 1884)

Microestola Gressitt, 1940: 180 type species *Microestola bidentata* Gressitt, 1940

Mimatimura Breuning, 1958b: 492 [HN] type species *Atimura ascoldensis* Heyden, 1884 (= *Cylindilla griseescens* Bates, 1884)

Pseudanesthetis Pic, 1929b: 119 [HN] type species *Pseudanesthetis apicalis* Pic, 1929 (= *Cylindilla griseescens* Bates, 1884)

parallela Gressitt, 1951: 515 (*Microestola*)

Tippmann, 1958: 59 - Asmar, 900 m, Kunartal, Nuristan, O.-Afghanistan; Bashgultal, 1100 m, Nuristan, O.-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 222 - Afghanistan.

Note. The occurrence of the species in Afghanistan is very doubtful as it was described from China (Hubei).

genus *Sophronica* Blanchard, 1845: 160 type species *Sophronica calceata* Chevrolat, 1855

Dasyo Pascoe, 1858: 253 type species *Dasyo lineata* Pascoe, 1858

Dasystola Kolbe, 1894: 63 type species *Dasystola hirta* Kolbe, 1894 (= *Sophronica carbonaria* Pascoe, 1864)

Dimbrokoa Pic, 1944: 16 type species *Dimbrokoa apicalis* Pic, 1944

Elithiotes Pascoe, 1864: 279 type species *Elithiotes hirsuta* Pascoe, 1864

Eupogonioides Fisher, 1930: 275 type species *Eupogonioides gardneri* Fisher, 1930 (= *Phunginus apicalis* Pic, 1922)

Lasiapheles Bates, 1873: 382 type species *Lasiapheles obrioides* Bates, 1873

Mimanaesthetis Pic, 1926: 16 type species *Mimanaesthetis atripennis* Pic, 1926

Phunginus Pic, 1922: 15 type species *Phunginus apicalis* Pic, 1922

egena Holzschuh, 2006: 488

Holzschuh, 2006: 488 - Est-Afghanistan, Nuristan, Baschgultal; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 227 - Afghanistan.

tribe Apomecynini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Apomecyna* Dejean, 1821: 108 type species type species *Saperda alboguttata* Megerle, 1802 (= *Lamia histrio* Fabricius, 1793)

subgenus *Apomecyna* Dejean, 1821: 108 type species *Saperda alboguttata* Megerle, 1802 (= *Lamia histrio* Fabricius, 1793)

Anapomecyna Pic, 1925: 29 type species *Anapomecyna luteomaculata* Pic, 1925

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Crassapomecyna Breuning, 1958b: 492 type species *Apomecyna crassiuscula* Fairmaire, 1896

Mecynapus J. Thomson, 1858: 187 type species *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856

Pseudoalbana Pic, 1895: 77 type species *Pseudoalbana lameerei* Pic, 1895

Vocula Lacordaire, 1872: 587 type species *Vocula irrorata* Lacordaire, 1872 (= *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856)

leucosticte Hope, 1831: 28 (*Callidium*)

lineate Pic, 1937: 14

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 228 - Afghanistan.

tribe Batocerini J. Thomson, 1864

genus *Apriona* Chevrolat, 1852: 414 type species *Lamia germari* Hope, 1831

subgenus *Apriona* Chevrolat, 1852: 414 type species *Lamia germari* Hope, 1831

Anapriona Breuning, 1949: 8 type species: *Apriona submaculosa* Pic, 1917

Cylindrapriona Breuning, 1949: 8 type species *Monochamus cylindricus* J. Thomson, 1857

Humeroapriona Breuning, 1949: 8 type species *Lamia swainsoni* Hope, 1840

Mesapriona Breuning, 1949: 8 type species *Apriona punctatissima* Kaup, 1866

Parapriona Breuning, 1948: 17 type species: *Parapriona brunneomarginata* Breuning, 1948

cinerea Chevrolat, 1852: 416

newcombei Gilmour, 1958: 112

Breuning, 1967a: 435 -Afghanistan, 25 km N von Barikot, 1300 m, Nuristan; Heyrovský, 1967: 157-Ost-Afghanistan, Prov. Nengrahar: Kamu, 1450 m; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 237 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 76 - Afghanistan.

tribe Exocentrini Pascoe, 1864

genus *Exocentrus* Dejean, 1835: 339 type species *Cerambyx balteatus* Fabricius *sensu* Dejean, 1835 (= *Cerambyx lusitanus* Linnaeus, 1767)

Bicolorihirtus Kusama & Tahira, 1978: 9 type species *Exocentrus venatoides* Kusama & Tahira, 1978

Formosexocentrus Breuning, 1958a: 322 type species *Exocentrus variepennis* Schwarzer, 1925

parrotiae Fisher, 1932: 304-306

klapperichi Breuning, 1957: 12

Breuning, 1957: 12 - Afghanistan: Nuristan, Kutiau, 1500 m; Tippmann, 1958: 59 - Kutiau, 1500 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan;

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Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 310 - Afghanistan; Lingafelter et al., 2014: 84 - Afghanistan: Nuristan, Kutiau; Holzschuh, 2015: 48 - Afghanistan.

tribe Phytoeciini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Paramallosia* Fuchs, 1955: 273 type species *Paramallosia afghanica* Fuchs, 1955

afghanica Fuchs, 1955: 274

Fuchs, 1955: 274 - Tarapas, Koh-i-Baba, Afghanistan; Panjao, Koh-i-Baba, Afghanistan; Ghilzai, Koh-i-Baba, Afghanistan; Schirparak, Koh-i-Baba, Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 302 - Afghanistan.

genus *Phytoecia* Dejean, 1835: 351 type species *Cerambyx cylindricus* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Parobereina* Danilevsky, 2018: 131 type species *Phytoecia vittipennis* Reiche, 1877

pashunica Lazarev, **sp.n.**

Afganistan, Bamian province, Waras district, 5 km SW Waras near Dahane Denawak village, 34°15'42"N, 66°52'43"E, 2680 m.

povolnyi Heyrovský, 1971: 82

Heyrovský, 1971: 82 - Darunta, province de Nengrahar, Afghanistan oriental; Skrylnik, 2010: 260, 261 - Afghanistan: Kaboul prov., Nangarhar prov.; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 302 - Afghanistan.

ochraceipennis Kraatz, 1882b: 337

Tippmann, 1958: 61 - Kutiau, Nuristan; 1500 m, O-Afghanistan; Kabul, 1740 m, O-Afghanistan; Bashgultal, 1200-1300 m. Nuristan, O-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 302 - Afghanistan.

tatyanae Skrylnik, 2010: 260

Skrylnik, 2010: 260 - Afghanistan: Bamian prov., Band-e Amir env. [34°50'59.64"N, 67°12'8.10"E]; Kabul prov., Paghman.

tekensis Semenov, 1896: 258

Fuchs, 1961: 259 - Gulbahar 1700 m, O.-Afghanistan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 302 - Afghanistan.

subgenus *Fulgophytoecia* Pic, 1900: 16 type species *Phytoecia circumdata* Kraatz, 1882

Pseudomallosia Breuning, 1967b: 1 type species *Pseudomallosia parterufipennis* Breuning, 1967

circumdata Kraatz, 1882b: 337

parterufipennis Breuning, 1967b: 2 (*Pseudomallosia*)

sellata Ganglbauer, 1887: 296

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Heyrovský, 1936: 212 - Gulan-Tal; Tippmann, 1958: 61 - Bazarak, Panchirtal, 2200 m, O-Afghanistan; Breuning, 1967b: 2 - Afghanistan: Hazaradjat, Koh-i-Baba, Pandjao Umgebung; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 303 - Afghanistan.

valentinae Skrylnik, 2010: 258

Skrylnik, 2010: 258 - C. Afghanistan, Bamian prov., Band-e Amir env.

subgenus *Opsilia* Mulsant, 1863: 387 type species *Phytoecia flavicans* Mulsant, 1851 (= *Leptura coerulescens* Scopoli, 1763)

brevicornis Kasatkin, 2013: 265

Kasatkin, 2013: 265 - Afghanistan, Bamiyan Prov., 8 km South of Bamiyan, Kohi-Baba Mts., Khushkak vill. env.

bucharica Breuning, 1943: 101

breuningi Dahlgren, 1988: 114

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 301 - Afghanistan.

Note. A series of specimens with the label: “Nurestan, N Waigal riv., 2000-3000m, IV-VII, 1971-73, O.Kabakov leg.” is preserved in the collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow).

subgenus *Pseudocoptosia* Pic, 1900: 16 type species *Phytoecia eylandti* Semenov, 1891

cinerascens Kraatz, 1882b: 337 (*Phytoecia*)

sokolowi Semenov, 1895: 206, 209 (*Phytoecia*)

Heyden, 1894: 83 - Afghanistan; Heyrovský, 1967:158 - Nord-Afghanistan, Prov. Herat: Bala Murghab, 470 m; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 292 - Afghanistan.

eylandti Semenov, 1891: 380 (*Phytoecia*)

glasunowi Semenov, 1895b: 207, 210 (*Phytoecia*)

Note. The species is undoubtedly distributed in Afghanistan, as it is very numerous in Turkmenia just on Afghanistan border (Kushka environs).

tribe Pteropliini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Niphona* Mulsant, 1839: 169 type species *Niphona picticornis* Mulsant, 1839

subgenus *Niphona* Mulsant, 1839: 169 type species *Niphona picticornia* Mulsant, 1839

indica Breuning, 1938: 239

grisea Breuning, 1938: 241

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Heyrovský, 1967: 157 - Ost-Afghanistan, Prov. Nengrahar: Samarchel, 900 m; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 316 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 195 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 73 - Afghanistan.

genus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842c: 370 [NP] type species *Mesosa bigibbera* Newman, 1842

subgenus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842c: 370 [NP] type species *Mesosa bigibbera* Newman, 1842

Acroptycha Quedenfeldt, 1888: 209 type species *Acroptycha spinifera* Quedenfeldt, 1888

Alyattes J. Thomson, 1864: 48 type species *Alyattes guineensis* J. Thomson, 1864

Cormia Pascoe, 1864: 281 type species *Cormia ingrata* Pascoe, 1864

Eurycotyle Blessig, 1873: 210 type species *Eurycotyle maacki* Blessig, 1873

Incamelomorpha Pic, 1926: 4 type species *Pterolophia depensis* Pic, 1926

Paralophia Aurivillius, 1925: 30 [HN] type species *Paralophia quadrinodosa* Aurivillius, 1925

Praonetha Dejean, 1835: 344 [NO] type species *Lamia crassipes* Wiedemann, 1823

Praonetha Pascoe, 1862a: 348 [HN, RN] type species *Prioneta albosignata* Blanchard, 1853

Prioneta Blanchard, 1853: 292 [RN] type species *Prioneta albosignata* Blanchard, 1853

Prionetopsis J. Thomson, 1864: 49 type species *Prionetopsis balteata* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Lamia inaequalis* Fabricius, 1801)

Theticus J. Thomson, 1858: 190 type species *Theticus biarcuatus* J. Thomson, 1858

***apicefusca* Breuning, 1938: 319**

Tippmann, 1958: 58 - Bashgultal, 1200 m, Nuristan, O-Afghanistan;

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 319 - Afghanistan; Kariyanna et al., 2017:

199 - Afghanistan.

tribe Saperdini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Glenea* Newman, 1842b: 301 type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831

subgenus *Glenea* Newman, 1842b: 301 type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831

Accola Jordan, 1894: 503 [HN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)

Accolona E. Strand, 1942: 392 [RN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)

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Cryllis Pascoe, 1867: 363 type species *Cryllis clytoides* Pascoe, 1867

Hapochoron Gistel, 1848: x [RN]

Sphenura Dejean, 1835: 350 [HN] type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831

afghana Breuning, 1971: 44

Breuning, 1971: 44 - Afghanistan: Shogran; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 324 - Afghanistan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 78 - Afghanistan.

genus *Saperda* Fabricius, 1775: 184 type species *Cerambyx carcharias* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Compsidia* Mulsant, 1839: 182 type species *Cerambyx populneus* Linnaeus, 1758

populnea Linnaeus, 1758: 394

populnea populnea Linnaeus, 1758: 394 (*Cerambyx*)

betulina Geoffroy, 1785: 78 (*Leptura*)

bilineata Scopoli, 1772: 102 (*Leptura*)

decempunctata DeGeer, 1775: 78 (*Cerambyx*)

populi Duméril, 1860: 607

salicis Zetterstedt, 1818: 258

Krivolutskaya & Lobanov, 1996: 132 - Afghanistan.

tribe Tetrocini Portevin, 1927

genus *Lenotetrops* Danilevsky, 2012a: 5 type species *Lenotetrops ivanovae* Danilevsky, 2012

ivanovae Danilevsky, 2012a: 6

Danilevsky, 2012a: 6 - Kabul prov., 13 km NW Kabul, Qargha environs, Band-e-Qargha; Wardak prov., W Maydan.

Phytoecia (Parobereina) pashtunica sp.n

Figs 1-2

Type locality. Afganistan, Bamian province, Waras district, 5 km SW Waras near Dahane Denawak village, 34°15'42"N, 66°52'43"E, 2680 m.

Description. A single female available; head, antennae and legs totally black; lower eye lobes about two times wider than genae; antennae a little shorter than body, not reaching elytral apices; 1st antennal joint short, about as long as 5th, 4th joint much longer, but shorter than 3rd; prothorax elongated, about 1.1 times longer than basal width; pronotum shining, glabrous, without glabrous callosities, without pale recumbent pubescence, without longitudinal setae stripe, with small sparse punctation; solitary white setae are distributed along sides of prothorax and under humeral elytral angles; scutellum triangula, without pale recumbent pubescence, with sparse small erect setae; elytra yellow with wide black area along middle; curved elytral margin with narrow black stripe, as well as anterior elytral margin; elytral punctation relatively big arranged in distinct longitudinal rows; elytral pubescence hardly visible, consisting of very short erect and recumbent setae; metepisternae with dense semierect short pale pubescence; claws brown, with very narrow sharp long denticles; ventral body side covered by shorte moderately dense pale pubescence, and looks black; last abdominal tergite rounded, sternite truncated; body length: 6.2 mm, width: 1.3 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The species is similar to 3 other *Ph. (Parobereina)* of the region: *Ph. (P.) ochraceipennis* Kraatz, 1882, *Ph. (P.) povolnyi* Heyrovský, 1971, *Ph. (P.) tatyanae* Skrylnik, 2010, but each of them has partly yellow tibiae or (in *Ph. ochraceipennis*) partly yellow femora; pronotum in all 3 species usually more or less covered by recumbent pale pubescence, with more or less distinct glabrous shining callosities; anterior elytral margin partly yellow (black tranverse stripe interrupted in the middle; black stripe of curved elytral margin never reaching humeri; pale elytral pubescence rather distinct; ventral body margin with very dense recumbent pubescence, looks white.

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Material studied. 1 female, each with 2 labels: 1) “AFGANISTAN 5 km WS Waras / Bamian prov., Waras distr. / near Dahane Denawak vill. 2680 m / 34°15'42.46"N, 66°52'43.20"E / Yu.Ye. Skrylnik 25.VI.2016.”; 2) “HOLOTYPUS / *Phytoecia (Parobereina)* / *PASHTUNICA* sp.n. / M.Lazarev det. 2019” - collection of M.L. Danilevsky.

Distribution. Central Afganistan, Bamian province.

Etymology. The Pashtuns are the largest ethnic group in Afghanistan.

***Phytoecia (Parobereina) heinzi* sp.n**

Figs 3-4

Type locality. Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, Swat district, Utrot, about 35°29'N, 72°28'E, 2300/2600 m.

Description. A single male available; head and antennae totally black; lower eye lobes more than two times wider than genae; antennae longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 2 apical joints; 1st antennal joint short, shorter than 5th, 4th joint much longer than 5th and about equal to 3rd; prothorax about 1.1 times shorter than basal width; pronotum with hardly distinct microsculpture and rather small sparse punctation, with very fine recumbent pale pubescence concentrated along middle forming pale central line poorly pronounced; without glabrous callosities; scutellum semicircular, with dense white recumbent pubescence; elytra black with elongated humeral yellow spots protruding backwards along anterior elytral third; curved elytral margin black; elytral punctation rather small, longitudinal rows are not regular, partly mixed; elytral pubescence hardly visible, consisting of very short erect and recumbent setae; metepisternae with dense recumbent white pubescence; legs yellow with partly darkened tarsi; claws with very narrow long sharp denticles; ventral body side covered by dense white pubescence, and looks white; pygidium shallowly emarginated, postpygidium rounded; last abdominal sternite slightly exposed apically, concave along middle; body length: 8.2 mm, width: 2.0 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The species is very close to rather variable *Ph. (Parobereina) vittipennis* Reiche, 1877, because of similarly colored antennae and pronotum, as well as similar pronotal sculpture,

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but in *Ph. (P.) vittipennis* prothorax more elongated, elytral punctation considerably larger strongly longitudinally arranged; many populations of *Ph. (P.) vittipennis* are characterized by long and dense pronotal and elytral pale erect pubescens; middle and hind femora in all populations of *Ph. (P.) vittipennis* with black bases; pygidium in the nominative subspecies and in *Ph. (P.) v. pravei* Plavilstshikov, 1926 deeply emarginated.

Material studied. 1 male, each with 2 labels: 1) “Pakistan (Swāt): Utrot 2300/2600 m / Heinz leg. / 15/19.VII.1997”; 2) “HOLOTYPUS / *Phytoecia (Parobereina)* / *HEINZI* sp.n. / M.Lazarev det. 2019” - collection of M.L. Danilevsky.

Distribution. North Pakistan.

Etimology. The new species is dedicated to Walter Heinz, who collected the holotype.

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AFGHANISTAN 5 km NW Waras
Bamian prov., Waras distr.
near Dahane Denawak vill. 2680m
34°15'42.46"N, 66°52'43.20"E
Yu. Ye. Skrylnik 25.VI.2016

HOLOTYPUS
Phytoecia (Parobereina)
PASHTUNICA sp. n.
M.Lazarev det. 2018

Pakistan (Swāt):
Utrot 2300/2600m
Heinz leg. 15./19.VII.
1997

HOLOTYPUS
Phytoecia (Parobereina)
HEINZI sp. n.
M.Lazarev det. 2018

2 **4**
Figs 1-2. *Phytoecia (Parobereina) pashtunica* sp.n.: 1 - Afganistan, Bamian province, Waras district, 5 km SW Waras near Dahane Denawak village, 34°15'42"N, 66°52'43"E, 2680 m; 2 - Labels of the holotype.
Figs 3-4. *Phytoecia (Parobereina) heinzi* sp.n.: 3 - Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, Swat district, Utrot, about 35°29'N, 72°28'E, 2300/2600 m; 4 - Labels of the holotype.

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